

Integration of CVD W- and Ta-based Liners for Copper Metallization

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Both TaN_x and WN_x are candidates for copper liner applications. A thermal CVD process for the deposition of WN_x liners, as well as both thermal CVD and plasma-assisted CVD processes for the deposition of TaN_x , have been developed, all of which are carried out at wafer temperatures under 425°C. The basic material properties, conformality, thermal stability, and integration and diffusion barrier properties of these materials make them appropriate for use in advanced copper-based interconnect applications.

Due to copper's high diffusivity into Si and SiO₂ and poor adhesion to most dielectric materials, refractory metal-based liners such as TiN, Ta, TaN_x, and WN_x are used to chemically isolate the copper from the dielectric. In particular, TaN_x (where x corresponds to a slightly nitrogen-rich stoichiometry) and WN_x (where x=0.5) appear to possess sufficient barrier properties for upcoming device generations.

Because of the high aspect ratios and complex geometries that will be encountered in advanced dual-damascene structures, liner conformality is of primary importance. Poor liner conformality requires deposition of a thicker liner to achieve a given bottom or sidewall liner thickness. Thicker liners increase the effective resistance of the line and, in more aggressive structures, lead to nonuniform Cu nucleation and poor filling. Advanced PVD processes such as [ionized metal plasma](#) (IMP) TaN_x can extend sputtering for a few more device generations, but it is believed that a CVD liner solution will likely be required for such applications.

WF₆-based CVD and plasma-assisted CVD processes for WN_x have been reported, but typically require either high deposition temperatures or high temperature anneals (>600°C) to yield films with low resistivity and low fluorine contamination. MOCVD TaN_x processes have been researched, but require temperatures in excess of 450°C to deposit films with resistivities below 1000 μΩ-cm. Compatibility with proposed low-k dielectric materials, many of which are thermally fragile, dictates a thermal ceiling of 350-400°C.

Accordingly, low temperature (<350°C), non-fluorinated CVD processes for both WN_x and TaN_x have been developed. The CVD WN_x is deposited thermally using W(CO)₆ and NH₃ as the reactants. Both thermal and plasma-assisted techniques for CVD of TaN_x films use TaBr₅ as the metal source. The thermal process employs NH₃ as the nitrogen source, and the plasma-assisted process uses a mixture of H₂ and N₂. This paper evaluates the films' material properties and copper diffusion barrier properties, demonstrating the feasibility of the materials and processes for advanced liner applications.

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Both types of films are deposited in dedicated, stand-alone 200mm wafer-capable tools. The systems are equipped with load-locks to prevent atmospheric contamination between depositions. Both the TaBr_5 and $\text{W}(\text{CO})_6$, which are room temperature solids, are delivered by a commercially available pressure-based mass flow controller. Tables 1 and 2 list basic film properties for the CVD WN_x and TaN_x processes, respectively.

Table 1: Thermal CVD WN_x properties

Resistivity (four point probe)	300-400 $\mu\Omega\text{-cm}$
Stoichiometry (AES)	W_2N phase
Crystal phase (XRD)	Amorphous or nanocrystalline
Contamination (XPS)	~3-5% each C and O
Step coverage (SEM, FIB-SEM, TEM)	>70% (0.2 μm , 6:1 aspect ratio structure)
Surface roughness (AFM)	<5% of film thickness

Table 2: CVD and PACVD TaN_x properties

	Thermal CVD	PACVD
Resistivity (four point probe)	2500 $\mu\Omega\text{-cm}$ (as deposited)	~150 $\mu\Omega\text{-cm}$
Stoichiometry (AES)	$\text{TaN}_{1.83\pm 0.12}$	$\text{TaN}_{1.00\pm 0.02}$
Crystal phase (XRD)	Amorphous	Cubic (111)
Contamination (XPS)	<0.5at.% Br	<2.5at.% Br
Step coverage (SEM, FIB-SEM, TEM)	>90% (0.13 μm , 8:1 aspect ratio structure)	>90% (0.2 μm , 6:1 aspect ratio structure)
Surface roughness (AFM)	<5% of film thickness	<5% of film thickness

Both thermal and plasma-assisted CVD TaN processes yield films with low levels of Br contamination (<0.5 at. % for thermal CVD TaN_x , and ~2.5at. % for PACVD TaN_x). The bromine is thermally stable in the TaN_x films up to at least 600°C. While the thermal CVD TaN_x process offers an as-deposited amorphous structure, the plasma-assisted process yields films with lower resistivities due to its less nitrogen-rich stoichiometry. The amorphous microstructure of the TaN_x films is thermally stable up to 600°C. Above this temperature, the film recrystallizes into a predominantly Ta_3N_5 phase.

At low deposition temperature (~200°C), the thermal WN_x CVD process yields films with a consistent W_2N stoichiometry and an amorphous (or nanocrystalline) microstructure. When the deposition temperature increases, the films become more crystalline. Adhesion of these

liners to SiO_2 is excellent, as measured by stud-pull testing.

The thermal stability of CVD W_2N samples was evaluated in a similar fashion: 500Å thick films do not recrystallize after 30 minute anneals at 650°C. For comparison, PVD W_2N films do recrystallize after such annealing.

The thermal CVD WN_x process and both thermal and PACVD TaN_x processes yield films with excellent conformality. Figure 1 is a cross-section FIB-SEM demonstrating the conformality of a ~500Å thick thermal CVD TaN_x film.

Figure 1. FIB-SEM of a ~500Å thick thermal CVD TaN_x film. Step coverage in the 0.13µm structure is >90%, and is similar for PACVD TaN_x and CVD WN_x films.

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We studied the barrier and general integration properties of these liners, particularly the adhesion and crystallographic texture of copper seed layers. These liners provide a good surface for the subsequent growth of CVD copper films for seed and fill applications (Figure 2).

Figure 2. FIB-SEM of CVD copper fill over 0.18µm structures coated with CVD liner.

Thermal diffusion barrier testing on these liners used the following methodology:

- Liners are deposited on HF-dipped Si substrates. The thickness of the CVD WN_x liners is 250Å, the thickness of the TaN_x liners is 550Å;
- The liner/Si stacks are characterized by RBS, AES (or XPS), XRD, and four point probe, both as received and after annealing. The annealing conditions are 30 minutes at 450°C, 500°C, 550°C, 600°C, and 650°C, in ~300 torr ultra-high purity Ar;

- 1000Å copper is sputtered on the as-received liners, and these stacks characterized with the same techniques as outlined above, again, both as received and after annealing with the method outlined above;
- The copper is stripped off using dilute nitric acid, and the films profiled by RBS for copper diffusion into the liner and/or Si substrate;
- The liner is stripped off using an appropriate chemistry, and a Secco etch performed.
- The films are then characterized for etch pits by SEM.

The 550Å thick thermal CVD TaN_x and PVD TaN_x liners appear to be stable up to 550°C, with both RBS and etch pit measurements indicating barrier failure above this temperature. Based on XPS, XRD, and RBS measurements, we attribute the barrier failure to thermally induced texture changes in the CVD TaN_x films. Analogous testing is currently being performed on PACVD TaN_x samples.

Similar copper diffusion barrier testing has been performed on 250Å thick CVD and PVD W₂N liners. As with the CVD TaN_x samples, the tungsten-based CVD liners are stable after 30 minute anneals at 550°C.

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CVD processes for the growth of WN_x and TaN_x liners have been developed. All processes are carried out at low temperature (200-275°C for CVD WN_x, 350-425°C for CVD TaN_x), allowing integration with low-k dielectric materials. The material properties and thermal stability of these materials make them attractive for advanced copper interconnect applications.

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